

**FORMATION OF URBAN CENTERS IN THE REPUBLIC OF
KARAKALPAKSTAN AND ITS HISTORICAL STAGES****Xodjaeva Gulya Ashirbayevna****Dauletbayeva Dilbar Dastanovna**

Karakalpak State University named after Berdaq

Annotation: This article presents information about the history of the origin of cities of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the stages of development of the urbanization process. It was studied in several stages, based on the periods of the emergence of cities and the processes of the shun period.

Key words: population, local population, settlements, city, township, antiquity, urbanization.

Introduction. The process of how urban areas form is not only fascinating from a geographical perspective; an analysis of this process and its outcomes is also essential to understanding how the region's territory is formed, how its resources are used, and how urban areas have developed historically. As a result, it provides, on the one hand, a chance to evaluate the system of urban areas' potential, without which it is impossible to predict how these areas would evolve. The geographic location of urban population centers has changed throughout time, but so has the network of these centers. The changes associated with the development points of urban population centers of different functional categories in this region are computed as a way to integrate the region's economy and culture on an economic and cultural level.

In Uzbekistan, studying urban development started in the latter part of the 20th century. Among the experts were O.B.Ata-Mirzaev, E.A.Axmedov, T.I.Raimov, S.Zokirov, N.M.Mamatqulov Z.H.Rayimjonov, A.S.Soliev, A.A.Qayumov, Z.T.Abdalova, Sh.B.Imomov, Z.M.Akramov, Sh.Zokirov, S.Islamov and other experts. The cities of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are not the subject of any direct

scientific works, however scholars such as Prof. E.K.Umarov, doc.G.Xodjaeva, N.Embergenov have discussed many facets of the republic towns, people, and economy in their dissertations and scientific publications. We can investigate the history of the urbanization of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in two different approaches in these scientific works.

Stage 1. Development during the former union (1926-1990 y);

Stage 2. Modern development period (1991-2023-y).¹

Having studied such scientific works, we decided to divide the development of the cities of the Republic of Karakalpakstan into five stages.

They are as follows:

Stage 1.. Ancient period (till 1926);

Stage 2.. 1926- 1939 y;

Stage 3.. 1939- 1959 y;

Stage 4.. 1959- 1990 y;

Stage 5.. 1991-2023 y.

While the cities of the Republic of Karakalpakstan emerged between 2.5 and 3 thousand years ago, the process of urbanization in Karakalpakstan started rather later. Throughout this time, the network of cities as a whole underwent several changes, as did cities with varying economic and geographical circumstances. According to the most important changes in the transport and economic-geographic conditions of the urban population centers, the development of the urban network in the studied area can be divided into several periods.

The main part. Stage 1. The ancient period covers the period before 1926. From antiquity to the asaleolithic period to the beginning of the 5th millennium BC-the beginning of the 2nd millennium BC, the people, mainly the amudarya Delta and the island, began to age in the deserts around the Caspian seas. By the 6th century BC, ancient centers of country-building began to appear. In the 4th century BC, after the

separation from the Achaemenid dynasty, a single ancient Khwarezmian state was formed. The written materials found in the cities of Qoylarqirilganqala, Ayazkala and Topraqqala, which are being studied at the moment, are proof that the palaces in Qoylarkirilganqala and Aqshaxanqala, Tuproqkala were the first cities in the territory of Karakalpakstan.

By the 12th and 13th centuries, the Xorezmshah had become the largest and most powerful country in Western Asia and the Middle East. During these times, necessary trade routes passed through the territory of Karakalpakstan to the neighboring countries in Asia, the Qipshaq field and the Volga river, and were of great importance in international trade.

In the middle of the eighteenth and nineteenth century, the majority of the Karakalpaks inhabited the middle and lower parts of the Syrdarya. By the mid-1800s, they had moved along the Yangidarya, the western branch of the Syrdarya valley, and the Karakalpaks, who live in the lower reaches of the Amıwdarya, were at war with the island's Uzbeks due to political events, namely the attack of Kazakh Khan Abulkhairkhan on the Karakalpak lands. Steppes separated the once-unified nation (Arol property), and its capital was initially Kungirost and then Shakhtemir (now Chimboy). The Karakalpaks were farmers by trade as well as fishermen.

The Karakalpaks were under the Khiva Khanate from 1811 until 1873, when Russian soldiers invaded Khiva and the Gandymıyan Treaty was signed. Following this, the Karakalpak territories on the right bank of the Amıwdarya were annexed to Russia, and the first All-Russian People's Account was held in 1897. Karakalpakstan consisted of just two minor towns: 3,100-person To'rtkul and 3,200 person Shimbay. There were just places like tiny craft workshops in these cities, and urban life was not enlightened.

According to the 1920 census, there were only two towns in the Amıwdarya region. To'rtkul is considered a regional city. It was formed in 1873 after General

Kaufmann's attack to Khiva. During this period, the population of the city was 3683 people. At that time, the number of Russians in Tortkul was the majority.

Shimbay was considered a district town. There would be more suitable for a big village rather than a city. They were distinguished from the villages around Chimboy by the density of houses, the presence of streets and their national composition. There was almost no "Russian element" here.

It was only 0.7% of the city's total population at the time. The low degree of economic growth, the absence of trade, the lack of railroads and other forms of transportation, and the republic's territory's separation from major trade routes are what define this.

The most important events of the first stage are: in April 1924, the autonomous region of Kazakhstan Karakalpakstan was established. In October 1924, Karakalpakstan became an autonomous region related to the demarcation of the national-state in the Soviet republics of Central Asia. The peoples of right and left sides were united into one region. In 1925, Kazakhstan was recruited into the ASSR.

Stage 2 covers the period from 1926 to 1939. During this period, namely in 1929, many local residents of Takhtakopir opposed the policy of coal farming. This was the main reason for the direct annexation of Karakalpakstan to the Russian Federation on July 20, 1930. In 1930, the region of Karakalpakstan was removed from the Republic of Kazakhstan and transferred to the RSFSR. In 1932, the government of the RSFSR decided to reconstitute the Karakalpakstan Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic. The capital of the republic was the city of Tortkól. From April 1 of this year, the city of Nukus was designated as the capital of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In 1936, KKASSR was transferred to the Uzbeksdan Republic, taking into account the people's political-economic relations and land-water conditions. As every republic has its own Constitution, after Karakalpakstan entered the RSFSR as an autonomous republic, its first Constitution was adopted in 1932.

On March 20, 1932, the autonomous region of Karakalpakstan was transformed into the autonomous Republic of Karakalpakstan, and from 1936 it was included in the Uzbeks. Among the cities that received city status during this period were Khojeli (1926), Shimbay (1926) and Nukus (1932).

It should be noted that the urban population of the Republic of Karakalpakstan has grown at a very fast rate compared to the rural population. In 1926, a total of 17,000 people lived in all urban areas of the republic, and the proportion of urban residents to the total population was only 5.1%.

Due to the specialization of Karakalpakstan in agrarian sectors, most of the people living there are rural people. According to the population census of 1926, the rural population of Karakalpakstan consisted of 94.9%, i.e. 314 thousand people. From 1926 to 1939, the population of the village increased to 103, 9 thousand people. During this period, the number of rural residents was 87.8%, and the average annual growth was equal to 2.2%.

Stage 3. Includes the years 1939 through 1959. The Second World War was in progress at this time. Taxyatas became a city during this time, officially becoming in 1953.

The number of people living in Karakalpakstan cities rose to 57,000 by 1939, a threefold increase from 1926. The city's population increased by 9.9% annually on average over this time, marking the biggest growth in Karakalpakstan's demographic history.

The population of Karakalpakstan reached 80,9 thousand between 1939 and 1959. The proportion of people living in cities was 27.2%. The city's population grew by 2, 3 times during the time period we looked at, with an average yearly growth rate of 4, 5%.

According to the development of the industrialization process, significant changes have occurred between the urban and rural population. Between 1939 and 1959, the rural population decreased by 46,5 thousand people, and the annual average growth

showed the opposite indicator (-0, 6%). It has mostly had a significant impact to this day.

In 1939, the urban network of Karakalpakstan consisted of 4 cities and one town. The city of Nukus was established as the capital of the Karakalpakstan Autonomous Region, while the former capital was the city of To'rtkul, formerly Petro-Olexandrovsk. The town of Qonirat, which is related to the regulation of urban networks, was turned into a rural settlement.

The war years and the post-war era, which correspond with the period of strong expansion and modernization of Karakalpakstan's productive forces, are characterized by the rapid rise of urban networks and population.

Stage 4. It covers the years 1959 through 1990. The good demographic circumstances in our nation throughout the post-war period paved the way for additional population growth. The average yearly growth rate of Karakalpakstan's rural population between 1959 and 1970 was 1.8%. After that, the rural population grew at an annual rate. But in recent times, this indicator has somewhat declined, and it currently stands at 0.7–0.8% annually.

Between 1959 and 1970, the city's population grew to 110.9 thousand people, and the share of the city's population was 35.5%. During this period, the annual average increased and it was equal to 5.5%.

According to the 1979 census, 378,500 urban residents were registered in the cities of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. This is more than 128,900 people compared to 1970. The population of the city occupied 41, 9% of the total population. The average annual growth of the city's population was equal to 4.7%. After 1979, this indicator began to slow down.

According to the last census, between 1979 and 1989, the population of the city increased to 205, 2 thousand people, making a total of 583, 7 thousand people. The share of urban residents was equal to 48.1% of the population.

In 1959, 5 cities and 4 towns were registered in Karakalpakstan, and 138,700 people lived in them.

Over the period of the following two decades (1959–1979), Karakalpakstan's urban network doubled and produced 19 urban centers, meaning 9 cities and 10 towns. The republic's urban population was growing at its fastest rate throughout this time. The towns of Qarataw, Jumirtaw, Kegeyli, Jasliq, Karakalpakstan, South Ustirt, and Kungirat, Moynaq, Mangit, and Beruniy emerged from the new cities [1, 35].

At the fourth stage of development, a new category of urban centers appeared here - towns (city-type settlements), which later received the name of a city.

Large settlements turned into cities and towns, which resulted in a migration of the rural people to the cities. They developed industrial output, and businesses in the construction, transportation, and allied services sectors opened and drew in workers.

During the period of the former union, the urban network of Karakalpakstan developed rapidly and during this period the number of its new cities reached 10, and the number of towns reached 16. The number of cities increased by 6 times.

Stage 5. It covers the period from the years of independence to the present day. In this period, the Karakalpakstan ASSR declares its state sovereignty in written by December 14, 1990. Since 1992, Karakalpakstan has become the sovereign Republic of Karakalpakstan, a part of the Uzbek SSR.

Aqsholaq and Qazanketken towns were established in 1993, and Elabad towns were established in 2006.

In 1990, the urban population of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was 599, 8 thousand people, and by 2000 it reached 721, 2 thousand people, that is, in 10 years, it increased to 121, 4 thousand people, an increase of 20, 2%. 48, 2% of all residents in general.

Between 2001 and 2011, the urban population of Karakalpakstan increased from 740,200 to 837,000 people, that is, to 96,800 people in total, the share of the urban population compared to the total population is 48.2% 50, increased by 2%.

Between 2011 and 2022, the urban population of Karakalpakstan increased from 837, 0 thousand to 954, 2 thousand people, i.e. to 117, 2 thousand people in total, and the share of the urban population compared to the total population increased from 50, 2% increased by 51.03%. However, this indicator does not show a very high rate of growth, it shows the permanent growth of the city's population.

The urban population grew at a significantly faster rate than the rural population during the time frame we studied (1926–2023).

The primary driver of the increase in the urban population is natural development; migration from villages and the transformation of certain rural regions into cities and towns account for a little portion of this growth.

It should be mentioned that Karakalpakstan's urban population is growing at a faster rate than Uzbek cities. Simultaneously, the percentage of Karakalpakstan's population living in urban areas, or the total urbanization indication, surpassed Uzbekistan's average indicator. Compared to Karakalpakstan, whose population growth has been 56 times greater, Uzbekistan's urban population has expanded 16.2 times since 1926. (2022)

By 2022, almost half of the population of the Republic of Karakalpakstan will be 954.2 thousand (49.0%) urban residents, and 994.3 thousand (51.0%) rural residents. The largest of the cities is the city of Nukus (01. 01. 2022. 329, 1 thousand people). It is one of the cities with the fastest growing population among the large cities of our country. The growth of the population of this city is caused by the merger of nearby towns (Qizketken) and villages, the process of "agglomeration". In relation to the geographical location of the cities, it is expanding day by day towards the south and south-west, that is, towards Amuwdarya.

To sum up, together with the cities of Xojeli and Taxyatas, as well as the other towns and numerous settlements, Nukus can eventually produce an urban agglomeration of roughly a half million people. In order to avoid the various issues that

are predicted to come in the future when cities and towns develop, a great deal of scientific and study work must be done.

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